

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN SPORTS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF BOYS AND GIRLS

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ABSTRACT:

The main objective of this study was to explore Emotional Intelligence in sports playing males and females. The sampling plan for this study comprised 100 samples (50 males and 50 females). The sampling technique employed to select the subjects for this study was the purposive sampling technique. The Emotional Intelligence Scale developed by Dr. Arun Kumar and Prof. Suraksha Pal was used to collect the necessary data for this study. The analysis and interpretation of this study have been done on the basis of the collected data. Several statistical methods, including the mean, standard deviation, and t test of significance, were used to analyze the data using SPSS. It was predicted that emotional intelligences would differ significantly between sporting male and female. The findings indicate a notable disparity in the emotional intelligence of male and female athletes. The findings of the research study also revealed that female sporting individual have better emotional intelligence as compared to male sports person.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Gender Difference, Male and female sports person.

INTRODUCTION:

One of the most popular research topics of the twenty-first century is emotional intelligence (Ashkanasy, 2003; Bar-On, 2006). This area studies how emotions influence a person's success or failure in their job and in life. First, Salovey and Mayer (1990) defined emotional intelligence as having three main skills: 1) assessing and expressing emotions; 2) controlling emotions; and 3) using emotions to solve problems. The first two skills focus on one and others, while the third involves appropriately using emotions to identify, evaluate, and resolve issues. According to Bar-On (2006), emotional intelligence involves emotional and social skills. These skills affect how we understand and express ourselves, how we understand others and interact with them, and how we handle daily demands, stress, and challenges. They also help us adjust to changing social and personal situations.

The term "emotional intelligence" describes a group of skills that show the ability to recognize your own emotions and those of others. It involves managing these feelings based on the situation. Emotional intelligence includes emotional empathy, awareness of your own feelings, and the ability to recognize your mood and the moods of others. It also involves controlling your emotions and responding appropriately in different situations, especially during stress. Good social and communication skills are also part of it, which means being

civil, considerate, and respectful in your interactions, (Panth, M. K., & Patel, A. 2015). Kamarajini, K. M. C., & Subramonia, G. (2018), Emotional Intelligence refers to the capacity for recognizing our own feelings and that of others, for motivating others, and for managing emotions well in us and in our relationships. Furthermore, we can describe Emotional Intelligence as the ability to distinguish the problem from a given situation or conditions and to find out ways in which to overcome such situations. Emotional Intelligence often operates on cognition or information processing that involves matters of personal and emotional importance to individuals and their relationships. Using emotions also involves the ability to harness feelings that assist in certain cognitive enterprises such as reasoning, problem solving, decision making and interpersonal communications.

Kumar, A., & Kumar, M. V. (2020). The ability to notice emotions, understand and generate emotions to support thought, comprehend emotional knowledge, and manage emotions for personal growth is called emotional intelligence. Performance is essential for emotional intelligence. Developing emotional intelligence will improve performance. Although it takes time, building emotional intelligence will lead to lasting changes in behavior. This will boost one's ability to control them and work with others. Alam, M. (2018), the ability to achieve positive results in relationships with others and with oneself is called emotional intelligence. Research in many fields, including psychology, education, management, and life sciences, has been shaped by emotional intelligence. As stated by Mayer, Caruso, and Salovey (2000), emotional intelligence refers to the capability to identify the significance of emotions and their connections. It also encompasses the use of emotions in reasoning and problem-solving. Having emotional intelligence enables individuals to manage their own emotions, comprehend the emotions of others, foster improved relationships, and make informed choices in both personal and academic contexts. According to another definition, emotional intelligence is the ability to recognize your own emotions and the emotions of others, to tell different emotions apart and label them correctly, and to use this emotional knowledge to make decisions about actions and thoughts (Coleman, 2008).

Emotional intelligence helps individuals solve problems in new ways and use their emotions to tackle everyday challenges. It relates somewhat to general intelligence. A person with strong emotional intelligence can recognize emotions in themselves and others, use emotions positively, understand their importance, and manage them properly in different situations (Kauts, D. S., 2018). According to Higgs (2000), emotional intelligence means recognizing our own feelings and handling them well. It includes the ability to motivate ourselves to finish tasks, use our creativity, and perform at our best. It also involves being aware of others and managing relationships successfully.

Douglas (2004) views emotional intelligence as a form of social effectiveness. It consists of skills that allow a person to read and understand others. One can then use this knowledge to influence others while pursuing personal and organizational goals. Emotional Intelligence is the ability to recognize our own feelings more clearly than others. It involves motivating ourselves and managing our emotions and relationships (Goleman, 2005). Woolfolk et al. (2008) defined emotional intelligence as the ability to process emotional information effectively. Emotional intelligence includes various skills that help people manage and understand their own emotions and those of others. This type of intelligence involves recognizing our feelings and using them to make good decisions in personal and work situations. It also affects the kinds of relationships that fit a particular job or profession. According to Goldman, emotional intelligence is the talent or skill that greatly influences all personal abilities. Emotional intelligence is the ability to recognize, access, and express emotions in a way that supports thinking. It involves understanding emotions and effectively

managing them to promote both emotional and intellectual growth. Performance is the foundation of emotional intelligence. As emotional intelligence (EI) develops, performance is likely to get better. Although it takes time, nurturing emotional intelligence (EI) will result in lasting changes in behavior. This will improve one's self-control and ability to collaborate with others (Raja, W. M., 2017).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Khan and Ishfaq (2016) found significant differences in Emotional Intelligence among teenagers based on gender, socioeconomic status, and the type of school they attended. Their results showed that female students usually had higher emotional skills, while adolescents from wealthier backgrounds and private schools demonstrated better emotional control and social skills. The research highlights how environmental and demographic factors influence emotional development. According to Adeyemo (2008), female employees in different companies showed significantly higher emotional intelligence than male employees. The study found that women had greater interpersonal sensitivity, empathy, and emotional awareness. These traits positively affected workplace relationships and job performance. To promote gender-balanced emotional skills and improve organizational success, our findings emphasize the importance of emotional intelligence training programs in companies.

In their study of 200 young people aged 16 to 19, Harrod and Scheer (2005) found a significant difference in emotional intelligence between genders. Females reported higher levels than males. The results highlight the need for targeted emotional development programs in schools, especially for boys. They show that teenage girls display better emotional awareness, empathy, and social skills. An analysis of emotional intelligence included thousands of men and women. It showed that women, on average, are more aware of their emotions, show more empathy, and are better in social situations. Men, on the other hand, tend to be more self-confident, optimistic, and adaptable. They also handle stress better than women. Generally, more similarities exist than differences. Some men are just as empathetic as the most socially aware women, while some women can withstand stress as well as the most emotionally strong men. Overall ratings for men and women suggest that their strengths and weaknesses balance out, making it a competition between the sexes. Studies reported by King (1999), Sutarso (1999), Wing and Love (2001), and Singh (2002) found that females have higher emotional intelligence than males.

Mandell and Pherwani (2003) looked into the relationship between emotional intelligence (EI) and transformational leadership style. They found a significant difference in EI scores between male and female managers. The study showed that higher emotional intelligence (EI) was associated with more effective transformational leadership behaviors. This emphasizes the importance of EI for organizational performance and management effectiveness. Using a sample of 200 participants ages 12 to 22 Petrides and Furnham (2000) studied the link between emotional intelligence and gender. The results showed that women scored higher than men in the social skill part of the emotional intelligence traits. This indicates that female participants had better interpersonal sensitivity, empathy, and communication skills.

Women are thought to have higher emotional intelligence than men because they are often more intimate and expressive in their relationships. Research by Duckelt and Raffalli (1989) and Sandhu and Mehrotra (1999) indicate that this difference arises from societal influences that socialize genders in different ways. Furthermore, certain psychological traits typically seen in girls might also help explain their greater emotional intelligence. Studies by Tapia (1999) and Dunn (2002) showed similar results. Research by Dunn (2002) and Tapia (1999)

shows that girls outperform boys in social obligations, empathy, and interpersonal interactions. Their interactions with parents, friends, and siblings are often more sensitive. Compared to boys, these traits help girls develop greater emotional intelligence. This research is just an initial step in understanding emotional intelligence. In general, people believe that women and girls are more emotionally sensitive and caring than men and boys (Eisenberg, 1994). Research shows that women usually have higher levels of empathy, caring behavior, and emotional sensitivity. This helps them adjust socially, interact better with others, and positively impacts the development of emotional intelligence throughout their lives.

METHODOLOGY:

Objectives: The objectives of this study are: - To study the emotional intelligence of boys and girls.

Hypothesis: 1: Male will score high on emotional intelligence than female.

2: There will be significant difference in Emotional Intelligence between boys and girls.

Sample: The current study is based on a simple random sampling of 100 people with sporting backgrounds. In addition, these volunteers were equally divided into two gender groups: boys and girls. The distribution of the sample is given below:

Table: 1

Groups	Frequency	Percentage
Group Male	50	50%
Group Female	50	50%
Total Sample	100	100%

RESEARCH TOOL:

The emotional intelligence tool was constructed by Dr. Arun Kumar and Prof. Suraksha Pal. which measure different aspects of emotional intelligence. Each item has a binary response category of "yes" or "no," which signifies complete agreement or disagreement with the given proposition. The instrument has both positively keyed and negatively keyed items. The score given for the presence of emotional intelligence is one point, while the absence is given zero points. In this study, the split-half and test-retest method have been used to measure reliability. The reliability of the test is found to be .89 and .81, respectively. Concurrent validity is obtained at .62.

ADMINISTRATION AND PROCEDURE OF THE STUDY:

After getting permission from the school administration for the collection of data, the researcher explained the nature and procedure of the research in brief to the students. Thereafter, the individual students were assured the confidentiality of the information they provided. The data collection instrument used was the scale developed by Dr. Arun Kumar and Prof. Suraksha Pal. Only the completed forms were used for the purpose of scoring, and the data was analyzed using SPSS (version-18). The T-test for independent samples was used to assess the difference in the level of emotional intelligence between male and female sports individual, also the investigator used the "t"-test to test the hypotheses.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Table 2 it can be observed; the data reveal the existence of a gender difference in emotional intelligence and its components. On the one hand, the scores of boys are, on average, 63.45 with a standard deviation of 42.22, while the scores of girls are, on average, 67.54 with a standard deviation of 37.59. On the other hand, the t-test with (df = 98) shows that the value of the t-test, 3.35, is significant at the 0.05 level, thereby proving the existence of differences in the overall emotional intelligence of children between the genders. Therefore, it can be concluded that male children possess significantly lower emotional intelligence than female children. This result does not prove the first hypothesis, which was that males would possess higher emotional intelligence than females. This finding also verifies the second hypothesis, which states that a major difference exists between males and females with regard to emotional intelligence. Moreover, the above chart also reveals that differences exist with regard to emotional intelligence as well as emotional regulation between male and female children.

It has been found that the emotional intelligence of boys and girls in secondary school varies a lot. The research findings are in line with the research by Sing (2010), Khan and Ishfaq (2013), Bhat and Khan (2013), and Nadeem and Nowsheen (2013), which found the overall emotional intelligence of higher secondary male and female students to be quite different. The research by the above scholars indicates that the overall emotional intelligence of adolescents is quite different for males and females.

Table: 2

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Sd	Df	t-value	Sig.
Emotional Intelligence	Male	100	63.25	42.21	98	3.35	0.05
	Female	100	67.54	37.59			

Moreover, Chu (2002) argues that men are more emotionally intelligent than women because emotional intelligence involves not only control and manifestation of emotional states, but

also social skills. The difference in emotional intelligence between men and women shows that men are independent, assertive, and able to control impulses and manage stress well, as well as being able to recognize their own emotions. All this is seen as a possible reason for men being more emotionally intelligent than women (Kaneez, 2006). The experiences of the male and female children were different from each other, which in turn resulted in a considerable variance in the development of emotional intelligence in the two groups. Thus, the importance of gender in the development of emotional intelligence has been recognized to be considerable. However, there is some controversy in the findings. Specifically, the study conducted by Babu and Rath in 2007, Mathur et al. in 2005, Pandit in 2004, and Bar-On in 2000 found that there were no gender differences in emotional intelligence.

The results obtained in the current study, in which sports students were used as the target population, show that there are significant differences in the level of emotional intelligence between the two genders, with the level of emotional intelligence in females being higher than that in males (Table 2). These results are in line with the results obtained in the previous studies, as discussed in the literature reviewed above, in which females had higher levels of emotional intelligence than males. The current study shows that there are significant differences in emotional intelligence between boys and girls who are athletes. The finding reached in this study was validated by previous research.

Conclusion: It was concluded from the results that there is a noticeable difference in emotional intelligence between male and female sporting persons. Female students have higher levels of emotional intelligence when compared to their male counterparts. The study revealed that women had higher Emotional Intelligence than men. Understanding this can provide a deeper insight into the emotions people develop and help in the psychological and educational support of emotional balance, which could indirectly influence the success of individuals in work and family life. Male and female sports persons have dramatically different emotional intelligences.

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Conflict of Interest: A conflict of interest does not exist in this research study.

REFERENCES:

1. Adeyemo, D. A. (2008). Demographic Characteristics and Emotional Intelligence among Workers in some Selected Organizations in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Vision -The Journal of Business Perspective*, 12(1), 234-240.
2. Alam, M. (2018). A study of emotional intelligence of adolescent students. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 6(3), 127-133.
3. Ashkanasy, N. M. (2003). Emotions in Organizations: A Multilevel Perspective. In Dansereau, F., and Yammarino, F. J. (eds). *Research in Multi-level Issues: Multi-level Issues in Organizational Behavior and Strategy*, 2, 9-54. Oxford: Elsevier Science
4. Babu, N., & Rath, J. (2007). Ecological context and development of children's understanding of emotions. *Psychological Studies, Journal of National Academy of Psychology*, 52(3). PP. 196-203.
5. Bhat, N.A. & Khan, M. A. (2013). Emotional Intelligence of adolescent Boys and Girls. *International Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 2(3), 67-71.

6. Bar-On, R. (2006). The Bar-On Model of Emotional Social Intelligence (ESI). *Psicothema*, 18, 13-25.
7. Bar-On R. (1997). Bar-On Emotional Quotient Inventory: Technical Manual, Toronto MultiHealth Systems
8. Bukhari, S. R., Fatima, S. I., Rashid, A., & Saba, F. (2017). *Emotional intelligence and self-esteem in male and female school students. The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 4(2). 137-145.
9. Chu, J. 2002. Boy's development. Reader's Digest. pp. 94-95.
10. Coleman, A. (2008). A dictionary of Psychology (3 ed). Oxford University Press.
11. Duckelt, E., & Raffalli, M. (1989). Taking care, maintaining the self and the home in adolescents. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 18(6), 549.
12. Dunn, P. 2002. The impact of starting a new venture on the entrepreneur and their family: Expectations, reality, and willingness to start again. Presented at the Association for Small Business and Entrepreneurship 2002 Annual Conf.
13. Douglas et al. (2004). Emotional intelligence of a moderator of the relationship between conscientiousness and performance. *Journal of Leadership and Organizational Studies*, 10(3), 2-13.
14. Goleman, D. (1995). Emotional intelligence. New York: Bantam Books.
15. Goleman, D., 2005. Emotional intelligence U.S.A: Bentam book.
16. Higgs, M. (2004). A study of the relationship between emotional intelligence and performance in UK call centres. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 19(4), 442-454.
17. Harrod, N. R. and Scheer, S.D. (Fall 2005). An Explanation of Adolescent Emotional Intelligence in Relation to Demographic Characteristics. *Adolescence*, 40(159), 503-512.
18. Kamarajini, K. M. C., & Subramonia, G. (2018). Emotional intelligence of boys and girls at the higher secondary level and their academical achievement. *Bodhi International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Science*, 2(2) 54-57.
19. Kaneez, U. (2006). Emotional Intelligence among the Individual with Depression
20. Katoch, A. (2013). A study of emotional intelligence of adolescent students in relation to the type of school. *International Journal of Behavioral, Social and Movement Sciences*, 2(3), 28.
21. Kauts, D. S. (2018). Emotional intelligence in relation to stress on boys and girls at the secondary stage. *MIER Journal of Educational Studies, Trends & Practices*, 8(1), 1-16.
22. Khan, M. A. and Dar, Ishfaq. A. (2016). Emotional Intelligence of Adolescent Students with Special Reference to High and Low Socio Economic Status. *Journal Natural Science*, 11 (3), 114-119.
23. King, M. 1999. Measurement of differences in emotional intelligence of preservice educational leadership students and practicing administrators as measured by the multifactor emotional intelligence scale. Dissert. Abst. Int. 60(3): 606

24. King, M. (1999). Measurement of differences in emotional intelligence of preservice educational leadership students and practicing administrators as measured by the multifactor emotional intelligence scale (Doctoral dissertation). *Dissertation Abstracts International*, 60(3), 606.
25. Kumar, A., & Kumar, M. V. (2020). Comparative study of emotional intelligence and intelligence quotient between boys and girls of secondary schools. *International Research Journal of Physical Education and Sports Sciences*, 7(2), February 2020.
26. Malik, W. R. (2017). Comparative study of emotional intelligence and intelligence quotient between boys and girls of secondary schools. *International Research Journal of Sports Glimpses*, 3(2),
27. Mandell, B. and Pherwani, S. (2003). Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership Style: A Gender Comparison, *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 17, (3), 387-404.
28. Mathur, M., Malhotra, B., & Dube, S. (2005). Gender differences of emotional intelligence and scholastic achievement, *Indian Psychological Review*, 64(3), PP. 133-136.
29. Mayer, J. D., Salovey, P., & Caruso, D.R. (2000). Emotional intelligence as zeitgeist, as personality and as a mental ability. In R.Bar-On and J.Parker (Eds), *The Handbook of emotional intelligence: Theory, development, assessment and application at home, school and in the workplace*. (pp.92-117). San Francisco, California: Josey-Bass Inc
30. Mokhlesi, V., & Patil, C. B. (2018). *A study of gender differences in emotional intelligence and learning behaviour among children*. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 6(4). <https://doi.org/10.25215/0604.047>
31. Nadeem, N. A. & Syed, Nowsheen (2013). Emotional Intelligence, Learning Styles and Academic Achievement of Adolescent Students of 10th grade. Unpublished Dissertation, Deptt. of Education. University of Kashmir.
32. Nasir, M., & Masrur, R. (2010). An exploration of emotional intelligence of the students of IIUI in relation to gender, age and academic achievement. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 32(1), 37–51.
33. Pandit, B. (2004). Gender Differences of Emotional Intelligence, *Shikshan samiksha, Educational Periodical*, 4(38), PP 59-62.
34. Panth, M. K., & Patel, A. (2015). A comparative study of emotional intelligence and intelligence quotient in between rural and urban undergraduate boys and girls. *IMPACT: International Journal of Research in Applied, Natural and Social Sciences*, 3(10), 1–10.
35. Petrides, K.V., Furnham, A. (2000). Gender differences in measured and self-estimated trait emotional intelligence. *Journal of Sex Roles*, 42, (5-6): 449-461.
36. Salovey.P & Mayer.J.D (1990).Emotional intelligence. Imagination, Cognition and Personality,9, 259-298.
37. Sandhu, P., & Mehrotra, N. (1999). Time pattern of female students with special reference to leisure time activities. *Indian Journal of Social Research*, 40(4), 285–296.

38. Singh, D. 2002. *Emotional Intelligence at Work: A Professional Guide*. New Delhi: Sage Publications.
39. Sutarso, P. 1999. Gender differences on the emotional intelligence inventory (EQI). Dissert. Abst. Int.
40. Tapia, M. L. (1999). *A study of the relationships of the emotional intelligence inventory (intelligence tests)* (Doctoral dissertation). Dissertation Abstracts International.
41. Venkatappa, K. G., Shetty, S. C., Sparshadeep, E. M., Parakandy, S. G., & Das, S. K. (2012). *Gender differences in emotional intelligence among first year medical students*. *Journal of Evolution of Medical and Dental Sciences*, 1(6).
42. Wing, E. and G.D. Love. 2001. *Elective Affinities and Uninvited Agonies: Mapping Emotions With Significant Others Onto Health*. Emotion, Social Relationships and Health Series in Affective Sci. New York: Oxford Univ. Press.